

Studies on Polycyclic Compounds. Part I. Syntheses of 2,7-Dimethylfluorene and 1,7-Dimethylfluorene-2-ol.

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A new synthesis of 1,7-dimethylfluorene-2-ol (XV), one of the degradation products of gibberellic acid, is described from β -(*p*-toluyl)- α -methylpropionic acid. A synthesis of 2,7-dimethylfluorene (VIII) by the same sequence of reactions has also been achieved.

Gibberellins¹, metabolites of *Gibberella fujikuroi*, are known to be powerful plant growth promoters. Gibberellic acid is the most active member of the group and has been shown to be a tetracyclic dihydroxy lactonic acid. One of the degradation products of gibberellic acid has been identified^{2,3} as 1,7-dimethylfluorene-2-ol (XV). In the present communication, we describe the syntheses of 2,7-dimethylfluorene (VIII) and 1,7-dimethylfluorene-2-ol (XV).

β *p*-Toluylpropionic acid (I)⁴ was condensed with aqueous formaldehyde according to the method of Rothe and Zimmer⁵ to afford β *p*-toluyl- γ -butyrolactone (II). The lactone was cyclised⁶ with sulphuric acid, when it gave 5-methyl-1-keto-2-indanylacetic acid (III : R=H).

1. Grove, *Quart. Rev.*, 1961, 15, 56.
2. Cross, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3022.
3. Cross and Melvin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3038.
4. Fieser and Dunn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 572.
5. Rothe and Zimmer, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 586.
6. House et al., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 4141.

The keto-ester (III : R=Me) was subjected to the Stobbe condensation with dimethyl succinate^{7,8}; the product on esterification gave the unsaturated trimethyl ester (IV). The ester was hydrolysed and decarboxylated by hydrobromic acid⁹ to give 2-carboxymethyl-3-2'-carboxyethyl-6-methylindane (V). The endocyclic structure (V) is rather preferred to exocyclic structure from analogy to 2-1'-carboxyethyl-3-2'-carboxyethylindane, synthesised by Bhattacharyya *et al.*⁸ by the same sequence of reactions. The acid (V) was hydrogenated over 10% Pd/C to 2-carboxymethyl-3-2'-carboxyethyl-6-methylindane (VI). The saturated acid on pyrolysis with load carbonate afforded 1:2:3:4:10:11-hexahydro-7-methylfluoren-2-one (VII). This was subjected to Grignard reaction with methylmagnesium iodide to afford 2-hydroxy-2:7-dimethyl-1:2:3:4:10:11-hexahydrofluorene; the crude compound on dehydration with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, followed by dehydrogenation over Pd/C yielded 2,7-dimethylfluorene (VIII).

β -(*p*-Tolyl)- α -methylpropionic acid¹⁰ was converted⁵ with aqueous formaldehyde to α -methyl- β -(*p*-tolyl)- γ butyrolactone (IX). This was cyclised⁶ to give α -(5-methyl-1-keto-2-indanyl)propionic acid (X; R=H). Stobbe condensation^{7,8} of the keto-ester (X; R=Me) with dimethyl succinate followed by esterification of the acidic product

gave 1-1',2'-bis-(methoxycarbonyl)ethylidene-2,1'-methoxycarbonyl ethyl-5-methylindane (XI). This was hydrolysed and decarboxylated^{7,9} to 2-1'-carboxyethyl-3-2'-carboxyethyl-6-methylindane (XII, R=H). The ester (XII, R=Me) on Dieckmann cyclisation gave 3-methoxycarbonyl-1,7-dimethyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofluorene (XIII). The β -keto-ester (XIII) was smoothly aromatised with methanolic acid to 3-methoxycarbonyl-2-hydroxy-1,7-dimethylfluorene (XIV : R=Me); similar phenomenon has been observed⁸ before. This ester (XIV) on hydrolysis, followed by decarboxylation with quinoline and copper bronze gave 1,7-dimethylfluoren-2-ol (XV).

7. Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2395.

8. Bhattacharyya *et al.*, *this journal*, 1964, 41, 479.

9. Sen *et al.*, *this journal*, 1959, 35, 751.

10. Bakh Dev, *this journal*, 1948, 25, 69.

EXPERIMENTAL*

β p-Toluyll-γ butyrolactone (II). A mixture of *β p*-toluyllpropionic acid* (19.2 g., 0.1 mole), K_2CO_3 (13.8 g., 0.1 mole), water (50 ml.) and 37% aqueous formaldehyde (10 ml.) was left at room temperature for 8 days. It was then acidified to effect lactonisation and the mixture was warmed on a boiling water bath for 30 min., cooled and extracted with a mixture of ether and benzene. The extract was thoroughly washed with 10% Na_2CO_3 solution and then with water. On removal of solvent, a yellowish crystalline solid was obtained (16.8 g.), m.p. 65-70°. The lactone was purified by distillation; yield 15 g. (77%), b.p. 180-85°/0.3 mm., m.p. 80-84°. A portion of the material was crystallised four times from a mixture of ether and petroleum (40-60°), and had m.p. 88-89°. (Found: C, 70.33; H, 6.03. $C_{11}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.58; H, 5.92%). Sodium carbonate extract on acidification gave 4 g. of unreacted acid, m.p. 124-26°.

5-Methyl-1-Keto-2-indanylacetic Acid (III; R=H).—The lactone (II) was cyclised with conc. H_2SO_4 following the procedure of House *et al.*⁶ Ice cold H_2SO_4 (conc., 20 ml.) was added dropwise, with shaking, to the lactone (II; 5 g.). The mixture was heated on the steam bath for 10 min. and then poured into crushed ice. The compound was taken in ether and extracted with saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate. The alkaline extract was acidified with HCl (cold, conc.) and the solid was worked up with ether to furnish the acid (4.6 g., 92%), m.p. 117-20°. A part (1 g.) of the acid was sublimed at 115°/0.4 mm. and the white crystalline solid (820 mg.), m.p. 124-25°, was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum (40-60°), and had m.p. 125-26°. (Found: C, 70.46; H, 6.06. $C_{11}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.58; H, 5.92%).

The semicarbazone of the keto-acid, was crystallised from a large volume of ethanol, and had m.p. 236-37° (decomp.). (Found: C, 59.98; H, 6.03. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires C, 59.96; H, 5.79%).

Methyl 5-Methyl-1-keto-2-indanylacetae (III: R=Me).—The keto-acid (III, R=H; 10 g.) was refluxed with methanol (30 ml.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 1.8 ml.) for 12 hr. to furnish the ester (9.6 g. 90%), b.p. 140-45°/0.4 mm., m.p. 48-50°. A portion of this ester was crystallised from petroleum (40-60°) and had m.p. 53-54°. (Found: C, 71.45; H, 6.51. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.54; H, 6.47%).

1-1',2'-Bis-(methoxycarbonyl)ethylidene-2-methoxy-carbonylmethyl-5-methylindane (IV)—Dimethyl succinate (11.63 g., 0.8 mole) was added slowly during 1/2 hr. under nitrogen, to a solution of potassium (2.2 g.) in dry *t*-butanol (42 ml) at room temperature. The yellow homogeneous mixture was added to the foregoing keto-ester (8.4 g., 0.4 mole) during 3 hr. and the mixture was stirred for further 2 hr. The deep-red solution was left at room temperature for 16 hr. The reaction mixture acidified with HCl (cold, dilute) and worked up in the usual way. The gummy acid (11 g.) was esterified with methanol (100 ml.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 6 ml.). After usual working up, the trimethyl ester was obtained as a straw-coloured oil (6.22 g., 46%), b.p. 195-200°/0.4 mm. A portion of the ester was evaporatively distilled at 150-55°/0.4 mm. to afford a colorless oil, λ_{max}^{EtOH} 270 m μ (ϵ , 13800) and 300 m μ (ϵ , 12300). (Found: C, 65.88; H, 6.52. $C_{19}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 65.88; H, 6.40%).

2-Carboxymethyl-3-2'-carboxyethyl-6-methylindene (V).—The preceding unsaturated ester (5.45 g.) was refluxed for 6 hr. with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (81 ml.), HBr

*All m.p.s and b.p.s are uncorrected. The u.v. spectra were recorded on Unicam spectrophotometer S.P. 500.

(48%, 55 ml.) and water (27 ml.). On concentration and cooling, the pale yellow solid was collected by filtration (4.0 g., 98%) and had m.p. 168-70°. A part of the material was crystallised from a mixture of ether and benzene to furnish the pure acid, m.p. 171-72°, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 262 μ (ϵ , 14900). (Found: C, 69.18; H, 0.27. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 69.22; H, 0.20%.)

2-Carboxymethyl-3-2'-carboxyethyl-6-methylindane (VI).—The unsaturated acid (V; 1.9 g.) was hydrogenated in 95% ethanol (55 ml.) over 10% Pd/C (200 mg.). Removal of catalyst and solvent furnished the saturated acid (1.9 g., 99%), m.p. 120-23°. A portion was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum (40-60°) and had m.p. 123-25° (Found: 68.67; H, 7.05. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 68.69; H, 6.92%).

1:2:3:4:10:11-Hexahydro-7-methylfluoren-2-one (VII).—An intimate mixture of the dibasi acid (VI; 0.9 g.) and lead carbonate (3.6 g.) on pyrolysis at 290-310° afforded the ketone, which was purified by evaporative distillation at 90-95°/0.3 mm.; yield, 465 mg. (67.7%). The material was evaporatively distilled again at 90-95°/0.3 mm. to afford an analytical sample. (Found: C, 83.72; H, 7.07. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires C, 83.96; H, 8.05%).

The semicarbazone was crystallised from methanol. m.p. 184°-86° (decomp.). (Found: N, 16.34. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{ON}_3$ requires N, 16.33%).

The 2, 4-DNI¹, m.p. 145-53° was purified through chromatography and crystallisation from a mixture of benzene and methanol, and had m.p. 155-57°. (Found: N, 14.42. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 14.73%).

2,7-Dimethylfluorene (VIII).—Methyl iodide (2 ml., 0.03 mole) was added dropwise to a stirred suspension of magnesium turnings (0.43 g., 0.018 mole) in ether. After some time when all the magnesium dissolved, the ketone (VII; 1.19 g., 0.008 mole) in ether (40 ml.) was added slowly to the cooled complex. The reaction mixture was stirred for 8 hr. and left over night at room temperature. This was then refluxed for 1 hr., decomposed with ice-cold ammonium chloride solution and worked up as usual to afford a brown-coloured oil (1.22 g.). To this crude alcohol (1.22 g.) in dry benzene (70 ml.), *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (0.47 g.) was added and benzene was slowly distilled off during 45 min. Some more *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.47 g.) and benzene (100 ml) were added to the residue and benzene was slowly distilled off leaving about 20 ml. of residue. The contents of the flask were taken in ether and washed successively with water, saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water. On removal of the solvent, the brown oil was evaporatively distilled at 83°/0.3 mm.; the olefinic compound responded to tetranitromethane test.

The above olefin (0.69 g.) was dehydrogenated with 10% palladised charcoal (265 mg.) to afford 2,7-dimethylfluorene (0.69 g.), m.p. 65-71°. This crude hydrocarbon was chromatographed on alumina (18 g.) using a mixture of petroleum (60-80°) and benzene (9:1) to afford crystals (0.59 g.; yield 50%, based on ketone VII), m.p. 105-108°. The hydrocarbon was further purified by sublimation at 100°/0.4 mm. followed by crystallisation from methanol and had m.p. 114-15° (lit.¹¹ m.p. 114-15°), $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 264 μ (ϵ , 19700). (Found: C, 92.62; H, 7.43. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}$ requires C, 92.81; H, 7.25%) The hydrocarbon (90 mg.) furnished 2, 4, 7-trinitrofluorenone complex, m.p. 182-84°, which on recrystallisation from a mixture of benzene and ethanol afforded red crystals (210 mg., 90%), m.p. 183-84°. (Found: C, 65.71; H, 3.61. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$ requires C, 66.01; H, 3.7%).

α -Methyl- β -(*p*-toluyl)- γ butyrolactone (IX).—A mixture of β -(*p*-toluyl)- α -methylpropionic acid¹⁰ (10.3 g., .05 mole), K_2CO_3 (6.9 g., .05 mole), water (25 ml.) and 37% aqueous formaldehyde (5 ml.) was left at room temperature for one month; 1 ml. of aqueous formaldehyde (37%) was added to the mixture at the interval of every 6 days. The reaction mixture was acidified to effect lactonisation, warmed on steam bath for 30 min., and worked up as usual to afford the lactone (7.5 g., 69.3%), b.p. 155-60°/0.2 mm. A portion was evaporatively distilled for analysis. (Found: C, 71.22; H, 6.48. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.54; H, 6.47%). The liquid lactone gradually solidified after four to five days, and had m.p. 85-95°. This was crystallised from ether, and had m.p. 100-101° (Found: C, 71.65; H, 6.75. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.54, H, 6.47%).

α -(5-Methyl-1-Keto-2-indanyl)propionic Acid (X, R=H).—The lactone (17.7 g.) was cyclised by warming with H_2SO_4 (conc., 51 ml.) on a steam bath for 15 min., the reaction product was poured into crushed ice and worked up as described before to afford the acid (12.2 g., 60%), m.p. 80-90°. A part of this material was sublimed at 80-85°/0.4 mm. and the white crystalline solid was crystallised six times from a mixture of ether and petroleum (40-60°), and had m.p. 110-17°. (Found: C, 71.32; H, 6.60. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.4; H, 6.47%).

Methyl α -(5-methyl-1-keto-2-indanyl)propionate. (X, R = Me).—The keto-acid (X: R=H; 10 g.) was esterified by refluxing with dry methanol (30 ml.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 1.8 ml.) for 12 hr. The ester had b.p. 135-37°/0.2 mm., yield 8.5 g. (80%). A portion was evaporatively distilled for analysis. (Found: C, 72.29; H, 6.80. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 72.39% H, 6.94%).

1-1', 2'-Bis-(methoxycarbonyl) ethylidene-2-1'-methoxycarbonyl ethyl-5-methylindane (XI).—To a stirred solution of potassium (1.9 g., 0.049 g. atm.) in dry *t*-butanol (36 ml.) was added dropwise, under nitrogen, dimethyl succinate (8.95 ml., 0.069 mole) during 1/2 hr. The yellow homogeneous reaction mixture was added during 3 hr. to the keto-ester (7.2 g., .02 mole) with constant stirring; which was continued for 2 hr. The deep-red reaction mixture was left at room temperature for 16 hr. and then worked up as usual. The acid (7.71 g.) was aried with benzene and esterified with dry methanol (100 ml.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 6 ml.) by refluxing for 24 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way to afford trimethyl ester as a straw-coloured oil (5.5 g., 49%), b.p. 183°/0.2 mm. A portion was evaporatively distilled to afford analytical sample, λ_{max}^{EtOH} 270 m μ (ϵ , 12170). (Found: C, 66.91; H, 6.75. $C_{20}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 66.65; H, 6.71%).

2-1'-Methoxycarbonyl ethyl-3-2'-methoxycarbonyl ethyl-6-methylindene (XII: R=Me).—The unsaturated trimethyl ester (XI; 5.4 g.) was hydrolysed and decarboxylated by heating under reflux for 6 hr. with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (69 ml.), HBr (48%, 55 ml.) and water (27 ml.). The acids were removed under reduced pressure; the residue after cooling was diluted with water and extracted with ether. After usual working up, the crude dibasic acid was esterified with a mixture of dry methanol (36 ml.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 3.6 ml.) by refluxing for 48 hr. to afford the desired product (4.5 g., 99%), b.p. 175°/0.4 mm. A portion was evaporatively distilled at 120°/0.2 mm. for analysis, λ_{max} 262 m μ (ϵ , 12020). (Found: C, 71.49; H, 7.59. $C_{18}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 71.50; H, 7.33%).

2-1'-Carboxyethyl-3-2'-carboxyethyl-6-methylindene (XII: R=H).—The foregoing dimethyl ester (500 mg., .0017 mole) was saponified with a mixture of NaOH (486.3 mg.,

.012 mole), water (1 ml.) and methanol (5 ml.), by refluxing for 4 hr. yellow acidic material (400 mg. 95%), m.p. 132-40°, was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum (40-60°) to afford colourless acid, m.p. 149-50°, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 262 m μ (ϵ . 11610). (Found: C, 70.07; H, 6.90. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 70.06; 6.61%).

3-Methoxycarbonyl-1,7-dimethyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofluorene (XIII).—2-1'-Methoxycarbonylethyl-3-2'-methoxycarbonylethyl-0-methylindone (XII, R=Me; 1.98 g., 0.0065 mole) in dry thiophene free benzene (8 ml.) was added to sodium methoxide prepared from sodium dust (0.30 g., .013 g. atom) and methanol (0.5 ml., .016 mole) in dry thiophene free benzene (8 ml.) and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 2½ hr. in an atmosphere of nitrogen. It was then cooled and just acidified carefully with HCl (cold, dil.) The reaction mixture was extracted with ether and the ether-benzene layer was washed with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate followed by small amount of water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The brownish oily residue, obtained after evaporation of solvent, on treatment with a few drops of methanol, and leaving in a frigidairo, furnished a yellow solid (1.2 g., 68%), m.p. 86-93°; it gave violet colouration with alcoholic solution of ferric chloride. It was crystallised from methanol, then sublimed at 80-85°/.05 mm. and again crystallised from methanol to afford pure, colourless material, m.p. 101-102°, λ_{max} 252 m μ (ϵ . 16490). (Found: C, 75.70; H, 6.97. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 75.53; H, 6.71%).

3-Methoxycarbonyl-2-hydroxy-1,7-dimethylfluorene (XIV: R=Me).—A solution of the aforementioned keto-ester (1 g., .0037 mole) in methanol (50 ml.) was acidified with 4-5 drops of HCl (conc.) and allowed to stand for 15-20 hr. at room temperature. The long yellow needles, separated, were collected by filtration and washed with a little methanol; the crystalline material (600 mg.), m.p. 110-15°, gave green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. This was crystallised twice from methanol, and had m.p. 110-15° and then sublimed. First fraction (100 mg.) sublimed at 80.85°/.05 mm, having m.p. 90-101°. This was crystallised from methanol to furnish the pure material, m.p. 101-102°, which remains undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample of keto ester (XIII). Second fraction (500 mg.) sublimed at 130-35°/.05 mm. having m.p. 140-45°. A part of this material was crystallised from methanol to afford pure, colourless, phenolic ester, m.p. 155-56°; it showed a green ferric reaction. (Found: C, 75.70 H, 5.99. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 76.10; H, 6.01%). The combined filtrate and washings, after separation of long yellow needles above, were concentrated and left at the room temperature for 3 days after addition of 2-3 drops more of HCl (conc.). This was then diluted with water and extracted with ether to afford a crude product (200 mg.). This was crystallised from methanol to afford the same phenolic ester (150 mg.), m.p. 135-40°; the total yield was thus 650 mg. (83.5%).

3-Carboxy-2-hydroxy-1,7-dimethylfluorene (XIV: R=H).—The phenolic ester (XIV: R=Me; 580 mg.) was saponified with KOH (1.1 g.), water (1 ml.) and methanol (17.5 ml.) by refluxing for 4 hr. The potassium salt was collected by filtration and washed with a little water. This was dissolved in water (300 ml) by heating, the solution cooled and acidified with HCl (conc.). The crude acid was extracted with ether; the ether layer washed with little water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of solvent gave a yellowish acidic product (300 mg.), m.p. 260-62°. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellowish solid, m.p. 263-64°. This was sublimed at 170°/.05 mm. to afford pale yellow phenolic acid, m.p. 263-64°, which developed a blue colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 75.30 H, 5.74. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 75.58; H, 5.55%). The filtrate and washings, after

separation of potassium salt above, on working up as usual, furnished the crude acidic material (85 mg.), m.p. 256-60°.

1-7-Dimethylfluoren-2-01 (XV).—A mixture of the foregoing phenolic acid (270 mg., .001 mole), quinoline (freshly distilled, 5.3 ml.) and copper-bronze (133 mg.) was heated, under nitrogen, at 220-30° (bath temperature) for about an hour and then at 250-60° (bath tempr.) for another hour. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual when a brownish solid was obtained. This was sublimed at 115°/0.2 mm. to give a yellowish material (190 mg., 87%), m.p. 185-90°, which gave a negative reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride. This, on crystallisation from benzene, afforded colourless crystals of 1,7-dimethylfluoren-2-01, m.p. 200-201° (lit.³ m.p. 202-204°, varied with the rate of heating). (Found C, 85.64; H, 6.71. $C_{13}H_{14}O$ requires C, 85.68° H, 6.71%).

The methyl ether was prepared by reaction with methyl iodide in acetone medium in presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 , crystallised from methanol, and had m.p. 167-69° (lit.³ 168-69°). (Found C, 85.63; H, 7.23. $C_{16}H_{16}O$ requires C, 85.68; H, 7.19%).

The acetate was prepared by reaction with acetyl chloride in dry pyridine, m.p. 145-50°. It was crystallised from methanol and then sublimed at 140°/0.2 mm. to afford the pure material, m.p. 153-54° (lit.³ 153-55°). (Found C, 80.96; H, 6.66. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 80.93; H, 6.39%).

The present work was carried out during the tenure of a scholarship awarded by the Ministry of Scientific Research & Cultural Affairs, Govt. of India. The author is indebted to Prof. B. K. Bhattacharyya and Dr. A. Chatterjee for their keen interest and encouragement in the work and Mr. B. Bhattacharyya for microanalysis.

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Received July 26, 1965.